

Complexes of Lead and Copper with 3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic Acid

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Potentiometric study of the complexes of bivalent metal ions, viz., Pb(II) and Cu(II) with 3,5-Dinitrosalicylic acid show the formation of 1:1 stable complex with Pb(II) and 1:1 (in solution) and 1:2 (stable) complexes with Cu(II). The stability constant of 1:1 complex of Cu(II) predominating in the pH range 2.5-4, has been evaluated from potentiometric titration data.

In continuance of our studies on the complexation tendency of 3, 5-Dinitrosalicylic acid (3, 5-DNS) with bivalent metal ions, viz., Ni(II)¹, Co(II)¹, Zn(II)², Mn(II)³, Cd(II)², and Mg(II)³, it was of interest to study the complex formation between Pb(II) and Cu(II) ions with 3,5DNS. A survey of the existing literature reveals the absence of any study on these systems. The complex formation has been studied potentiometrically. The Calvin and Melchior's⁴ extension of Bjerrum's⁵ method has been used for calculating the stability constant from potentiometric titration data.

EXPERIMENTAL

Anal-R B.D.H. reagents lead nitrate, copper sulphate, sodium hydroxide and Riedel's 3, 5-DNS were used and their solutions prepared in double distilled water.

pH titrations were made with Cambridge bench pattern pH meter. A glass electrode of the range 0-14 pH was used in conjunction with saturated calomel electrode.

To establish the stoichiometry of the complex species formed during the interaction of metal ions with 3, 5-DNS, the magnitude of proton displacement was determined by titrating solutions containing metal and ligand in different ratios against standard alkali. The titration curves for Pb(II) and Cu(II) complexes are shown in figs. 1 2, respectively.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Lead: Curve-1, fig. 1, indicates two inflections corresponding to the neutralization of -COOH and -OH groups of the ligand. When an equimolecular concentration of lead nitrate is added, a sharp inflection at $m = 2$ is obtained (curve-2, fig. 1) which indicates the formation of 1:1 complex as follows:

1. S. S. Dube and S. S. Dhindsa, *Indian J. Chem.* (in press).
2. S. S. Dube and S. S. Dhindsa, *Current Science* 1969, **38** (6), 140.
3. S. S. Dube and S. S. Dhindsa, *Z. Naturforsch.* (in press).
4. M. Calvin and N. G. Melchior, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
5. J. Bjerrum, "Metal Amine Formation in Aqueous Solution" P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.

When 2:1 mixture of ligand to metal is titrated against standard alkali, two inflections at $m = 3$ and 4 are obtained (curve-3, fig. 1). First inflection corresponds to the formation of 1:1 complex and neutralization of $-\text{COOH}$ group of the excess ligand and second inflection corresponds to the neutralization of $-\text{OH}$ group.

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titration curves of 3,5-DNS in the absence and presence of Pb(II) against 0.1 M NaOH. (Total vol. of sol. = 20 ml.)

Curve 1, $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ 3,5-DNS;

Curve 2, $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ 3,5-DNS + $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$;

Curve 3, $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ 3,5-DNS + $5 \times 10^{-3} M$ $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

The complex PbA which is precipitated in the solution, was filtered, washed and dried. The quantitative analysis further confirmed the formation of 1:1 complex. Lead was estimated gravimetrically as lead sulphate⁶ and was found to be 48.4% in the complex (required, 47.8%).

Copper : Two inflections (curve-1, fig. 2) corresponds to the neutralization of $-\text{COOH}$ and $-\text{OH}$ groups of the ligand respectively. When 1:1 mixture of the ligand and metal is titrated against standard alkali, two inflections at $m = 2$ and 3 are obtained (curve-2, fig. 2).

6. Arthur I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis."

The first inflection corresponds to the formation of 1:1 complex and second inflection corresponds to the disproportionation of 1:1 complex into more stable 1:2 complex and copper hydroxide, according to the following reactions;

Greenish white gelatinous ppt. begins to appear above pH 4.

Fig. 2.—Potentiometric titration curves of 3,5-DNS in the absence and presence of Cu(II) against 0.1M NaOH (total vol. of sol. = 20 ml.)
 Curve 1, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ 3,5-DNS;
 Curve 2, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ 3,5-DNS + $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ CuSO_4 ;
 Curve 3, $1 \times 10^{-2}M$ 3,5-DNS + $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ CuSO_4 ;
 Curve 4, $1.5 \times 10^{-2}M$ 3,5-DNS + $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ CuSO_4 .

When 2:1 mixture of ligand and metal is titrated against standard alkali, a sharp inflection at $m = 4$ is obtained (curve-3, fig. 2), corresponding to the formation of stable 1:2

complex as follows :

Precipitates begins to appear above pH 4.

When 3:1 ratio is titrated against standard alkali, two inflections at 5 and 6 moles of NaOH/mole of ligand are obtained, first corresponding to the formation of 1:2 complex and neutralization of -COOH group of the excess ligand and second corresponding to the neutralization of -OH group.

Fig 3.—Potentiometric titration curves of 3,5-DNS in the absence and presence of Cu(II) against 0.1M NaOH.
 Curve 1, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ 3,5-DNS;
 Curve 2, $5 \times 10^{-3}M$ 3,5-DNS + $1.25 \times 10^{-3}M$ CuSO_4 .

The stability of the 1:1 complex which predominates in the pH range 2.5-4 was determined by applying the Calvin and Melchior's extension of Bjerrum's method. The \bar{n} (which defined as the average number of ligand molecules bound per atom) values were evaluated from fig. 3. The horizontal distance between curves 1 and 2 measures quite accurately the additional base consumed or the total number of A^{--} complexed. This number divided by total Cu^{++} is \bar{n} . At any pH, $[\text{A}^{--}]$ was calculated as :

$$[\text{A}^{--}] = \frac{[\text{H}_2\text{A}]_{\text{Total}} - [\text{RA}]}{\frac{[\text{H}^+]^2}{K_1 K_2} + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_2} + 1} \quad \dots (5)$$

Where K_1 and K_2 are the first and second dissociation constants of the ligand.⁷ A plot between \bar{n} and $-\log[A^{--}]$ gives the formation curve, (fig. 4). The value of $\log K$ was read directly at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and was found to be 7.0.

Fig. 4.—Plot of \bar{n} against $-\log[A^{--}]$.

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